

Practices and Difficulties Encountered by Liga Organizers in the Conduct of Liga ng Bayan

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the practices and difficulties of the Liga Organizers in conducting Liga ng Bayan. Interviews with the Liga Organizers were done in order to determine their training needs and come up with the most appropriate training program/activities to improve their knowledge in the conduct of liga in their respective barangay. The study concluded that the Liga Organizers have good practices in conducting Liga ng Bayan such as holding meetings and making plans in preparation for the game proper, supervising during the game proper, and holding awarding ceremonies and post evaluation after the games. The difficulties encountered by the Liga Organizers consist mainly of misunderstandings among players, alleged biases of the referees, and rules on set qualifications for players. The Liga Organizers expressed their need for assistance especially on the provision of sports clinic. Results of the study were used to make recommendations to maximize the benefits that can be derived from the best way to conduct/implement Basketball Liga in the barangay through the application of a Standardized Manual of Operation and Guidelines where all the important details in the conduct of Liga are found. Liga Organizers should have a common rules and standard in the proper selection of officiating officials. Sports clinic should be conducted and facilitated by recognized basketball experts before and after the liga. This study also has implications on the health and wellness practice of the residents in the different barangays in Nueva Vizcaya.

Keywords: health and wellness, sports popularity

INTRODUCTION

The popularity or mass appeal of basketball around the world is undisputed (Ostojic, Mazic, & Dikic, 2006; talkbasketstaff, 2017), which is reflected in its large viewership in the actual venue or on TV. Several surveys have been conducted to determine the most popular sport, and in almost all of these surveys, basketball managed to be on the top 10. Basketball has been ranked the second most popular sport in the world, behind football (Stevenson, 2010) or soccer (Dela Cruz, 2017), 7th with 825 million fans (World Atlas, 2018), and 9th in a different survey conducted by sportyghost.com.

To Filipinos, basketball is a way of life. It is the number one game (Grundy, Nelson & Dyreson, 2014). Almost anywhere in the Philippines, one sees a basketball court (Henson, 2016). It can be seen in almost every street. Most basketball courts are modern but there are also makeshift basketball courts like those found in barangay plazas, or even those single courts found in ordinary homes.

In the Philippines, basketball is not only popular but has been elevated to nearly a religion. It is a sport that has practically unified the country more effectively than any politician (Ronquillo, 2017) as Filipino basketball fanatics establish a close bond with each other to give support to their choice of basketball teams or basketball idols.

This practice of capitalizing on the popularity of basketball to unite people, according to Antolihao (2017), is one of the legacies of American colonialism (Grundy, Nelson & Dyreson, 2014). Accordingly, our American colonizers introduced basketball through the physical education programs in schools. They discovered the effectiveness of spreading modern sports as a means to "bind" their colonial subjects "more firmly and more happily to their rule." Since then, basketball was used to introduce new social behaviors and moral standards and encouraged a conformity that helped the colonizers maintain control over their colonies. Surprisingly, Filipinos took a liking to the sport, whether as players or spectators.

In almost all barangays in the Philippines, Liga is organized as part of their summer activities and barangay fiesta. It is part of socialization and a way of convening the barangay

people in their plaza or community center. The organizers, usually the barangay officials and *Sangguniang Kabataan*, chose basketball because they believe that it is a well-liked sport. There is no formal conduct of the game compared with the highly organized tournaments in the cities. What they have in mind is just to have enjoyment and fun for both the players and the barangay people.

From the preliminary observation and interview conducted, in the barangays of Bayombong, liga is usually conducted during the months of August - October in preparation for the upcoming Inter-Barangay Mayor's Cup conducted at LGU Gym. There are 25 barangays of Bayombong but only or around 10-16 participate in the Inter Barangay because of some reasons such as the proximity of the playing venue from the barangay, lack of transportation, accessibility, budget, since most of the barangays are IRA (Internal Revenue Allotment) dependent.

In the conduct of the Liga ng Barangay, the point persons are the barangay *kapitan*, barangay *kagawad* in charge of the Committee on Sports & Development and the *Sangguniang Kabataan*. The liga players are the bonafide residents of the barangay or at least have resided in the barangay for about six months and did not join or compete in national basketball competition. The Liga has different brackets: Kiddies with players aged 12 below, Cubs with players aged 13-15 below, Midgets with players 16-17 years old, Juniors with players aged 18-21 years below and Seniors with players aged 22 years below. The barangay Liga objectives include providing kids and young people with worthwhile activities, nurturing the passion of the players, encouraging participation in the Inter Barangay Mayor's Cup and involving the community members.

Findings in the previous research conducted by Bulatao et al. (2018) indicated that liga organizers in the barangay did not have written rules and guidelines in the actual or detailed conduct of the liga. Most often than not, the organizers were dependent solely on the official referees who were paid to run the liga from beginning to end. Activities conducted before, during, and after the tournament were not properly recorded and documented. What the organizers have was general information on how to do it but there no specific rules have been written or documented, thus the need to conduct training for the liga organizers and equip them in conducting the liga ng bayan on their own is deemed necessary. All these enumerated reasons can only be addressed with a well-crafted Manual of Operations and Guidelines (MOPG). The MOPG contains all the necessary information needed in conducting a liga from planning to implementation to evaluation. According to Ahmed (2019), manuals are universal documents that can be understood by ordinary people. It explains certain operations and processes of different departments. With a manual, company or any organization can have a standard for its operations. Similarly, in a basketball liga, with an MOPG on hand, it is expected that the conduct of barangay liga will be done as smoothly as expected.

The observations cited above inspired the researchers to dwell on this subject –Practices and Difficulties Encountered by Liga Organizers in the Conduct of Liga ng Bayan. Results may be used to forward recommendations on how to conduct the liga through the implementation of the Manual of Operations and Guidelines so that organizers and players can maximize the benefits of organizing and playing the game.

Conceptual and Analytical Framework

The discussions of the theory presented herewith are the related theories connected to the present study. The principle of pragmatism claims that the meaning of ideas lies in its practical consequences; it means that students must interact with their environment in order to adapt and learn. Pragmatism in education and in modern perspective is credited to Professor John Dewey. This philosophy is very much related to experimentalism. It is derived from the Greek '*pragma*' meaning a thing done, a fact that is practiced. According to the pragmatist, the aim of education is the total development of the child through experiencing or through self-activity or the *learning by doing*. Pragmatists also suggest that the curriculum must offer subjects or provide opportunities for various projects and activities that are relevant to the needs, abilities, and interests as well as the socio-economic conditions of the learners. They further believed that it must be a learner-centered for all educative process. This concept is based on Dewey's principle where education is life, education is growth, education is a social process and education is the construction of human experience (Duka, 1999).

According to Tamayo (2013), learning to do is the development of the hand and focus on

skills and actions. This requires person to act properly in any kind of situation. Learning to do implies that students learn best when they do or apply what they know. This is related to what Confucius remarked: *I hear, and I forget. I see and I remember. I do and I understand.* Learning to do is very much related to learning by doing as supported by John Dewey.

On the other hand, the Observational Learning which states that performers learn new competencies by observing others. They learn through demonstrations that can be used as role model to follow (Bandura). According to him, there are 4 stages of this theory. Which is Attention, wherein the performers need to watch suitable demonstration of the skill; Retention, creating the mental image of the necessary skill. Practice your mind skill over and over to make the right movements in the right order. And also, motor production included where students must be able to repeat the skills first or through a series of progression; And lastly is that, there must be motivation in order for the learners to replicate the skilled action.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

The figure above summarizes the main focus of the study. Information regarding the practices of the Liga Organizers in conducting Liga ng Bayan and the difficulties they have encountered were gathered through interviews. This information on the conduct of the Liga ng Bayan is fundamental in every community activity inasmuch as this information will be of great help in standardizing the conduct of barangay basketball liga. The terminal goal of the study was to craft a Manual of Operations and Guidelines to improve the conduct of Liga ng Bayan.

The main goal of this study was to determine the level of knowledge of the liga organizers in conducting the liga ng bayan.

Specifically, this study sought to determine the following:

1. How long have the respondents been organizing Liga ng Bayan?
2. What preparations do the respondents usually conduct before, during, and after the Liga ng Bayan?
3. What difficulties did the respondents encounter in organizing the Liga ng Bayan?
4. What specific part of a basketball tournament the respondents would like to be trained on?

METHODOLOGY

This study used the qualitative design. Interviews were conducted to determine the practices of Liga organizers in conducting Liga ng bayan and the difficulties they have encountered through phone interviews. The results of the interview served as basis in crafting Manual of Operations and Guidelines to improve the conduct of Liga ng Bayan.

The main respondents of this study were the liga organizers (*barangay kapitans, kagawad, sangguniang kabataan* representatives) of the different barangays of Bayombong. To determine the participants, purposive sampling was utilized as only those who organized their barangay basketball liga were included.

The study covered the ten selected barangays of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, namely *Buenavista, Bonfal Proper, Casat, Don Domingo Maddela, Don Mariano Marcos, Luyang, Masoc, Salvacion, San Nicolas, and Vista Alegre.* These ten barangays are regularly conducting liga as one of

the highlights of their barangay fiesta and summer activities. Based on the result of the previous research, liga is already part of their tradition. It serves as the favorite pastimes, bonding moments, and relaxation activity of the barangay people. The main objective of the liga is to develop the young people's awareness on the importance of sports as a way of life and eventually help them focus their life to worthwhile activities rather than engaging in vices. Nucom cited the significance of the of liga or basketball tournament in channeling the strength, strategy and wisdom of youth, especially out-of-school youth to a more productive and worthwhile recreational activities and avert them from engaging in illegal activities.

The conduct of liga is usually the task of a barangay *kagawad* in charge of sports development of the barangay. It was also mentioned in the previous research that Liga is important as it also an avenue to train players to represent their barangay in higher competition conducted by the municipality.

Phone interviews with barangay basketball liga organizers (barangay *Kapitan*, *Kagawad* in charge of Sports Development and *Sangguniang Kabataan* representatives) were conducted using an interview guide consisting of four questions.

In the data gathering procedure, guide questions for the needs' assessment were formulated. After which contact numbers of the identified barangay *kapitans* from the President of the Association of Barangay Captain (ABC) via messenger chat and via call were sought. Personal messages to the barangay *kapitan* via SMS where introduction, purpose of the study and possible result of the study, and schedule of the phone interview were mentioned. Actual phone interviews with barangay basketball liga organizers which lasted from 7-14 minutes were conducted.

Data were analyzed qualitatively. Qualitative responses from the interview were coded and categorized thematically. Specifically, it utilized the six (6) step-by-step data analysis process for qualitative research as recommended by Creswell (2009) such as; (1) to transcribe the interviews, (2) read through all the data to obtain a general sense of the information and reflect on its overall meaning, (3) code the data into chunks or segments of texts, (4) describe the themes, (5) make narrative passages to convey the findings, (6) make interpretations of the meaning of the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Section 1. Profile of Respondents

Table 1 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of age, highest educational attainment, and number of years of organizing Liga ng Bayan.

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents

Profile	f	%
Age		
25-40	1	10
40-59	7	80
60-70	2	10
Total	10	100
Highest Educational attainment		
College level	3	30
College Graduate	6	60
Master's Degree	1	10
Number of years of Organizing Liga ng Bayan		
1-10	4	40
11-20	4	40
21-30	2	20

As shown in the table, majority (80%) of the Liga Organizers were aged 40-60 years old. This indicates that majority of the Liga Organizers are middle aged. In terms of highest educational attainment, majority (60%) of the Liga Organizers were college graduates whereas in terms of their number of years organizing Liga ng Bayan, majority have organized Liga ng Bayan

for 1-10 years (40%) and 11-20 years (40%), respectively. In addition, majority of the barangay *kapitans* of Bayombong are male, there are only two females.

Section 2. Liga Organizers' Practices in Conducting Liga ng Bayan Before, During, and After the Activity

Table 2 presents the Liga Organizers' practices in conducting liga ng bayan before, during, and after the activity.

Table 2. Practices in Conducting Liga ng Bayan Before, During, and After the Activity

		f	%
Activities Before the Liga	Meeting to discuss / orient players rules and regulations	6	60
	Preparation such as practices	1	10
	Organize division	1	10
	Clinic by officiating officials	1	10
	Present the minutes of the meeting to the community through notices, set deadlines for submission, set qualifications	1	10
	Profiling of players	1	10
	Opening program to orient players on the ground rules	1	10
	Meeting for costing of the activity, payment for referred, materials to be used	1	10
	Check activity design	1	10
	Make deal with referees, costing	1	10
During the Liga ng Bayan	Supervision	8	80
	Moral support	1	10
	Intervention of barangay officials when problems arise	2	20
	In case problems arise, the team writes a petition letter addressed to the organizing committee	1	10
After the Liga ng Bayan	Awarding	7	70
	Post activity evaluation	2	20
	Salusalo	1	10

As shown in the table, before a Liga ng Bayan was conducted, majority (60%) of the Liga Organizers held meetings to discuss and orient players on the rules and regulations of the activity. As one Liga Organizer stated, "*Bago agpa liga, planning, meeting kami*". This was affirmed by another Liga Organizer who remarked, "*Usually before mag start ang laro pina patawag ko lahat ng players at coaches, in front of the referee, so yun muna, sasabihin mo na lahat ng rules in and out of the court*".

Other activities done prior to the game proper consisted of preparation such as practices, organization of division, clinic of officiating officials, presentation of the minutes of the meeting to the community through notices, setting deadlines for submission, setting qualifications, profiling of players, conducting opening program to orient players on the ground rules, meeting for costing of the activity, payment for referees, materials to be used, checking activity design, and making deal with referees especially on costing.

The table also shows that majority (80%) of the Liga Organizers provided supervision during the game proper and they intervened when disagreements occurred and whenever necessary.

After the game, 70% of the respondents stated that they held awarding ceremonies while 20% conducted post evaluation activity and 10% mentioned "*salusalo*" or community fellowship.

Section 3. Difficulties Encountered by Liga Organizers in Conducting Liga ng Bayan

Table 3 shows the difficulties encountered by Liga Organizers in conducting Liga Ng Bayan.

Table 3. Difficulties Encountered by Liga Organizers in Conducting Liga ng Bayan

Difficulties Encountered in Conducting Liga ng Bayan	f	%
No manual of operations and guidelines but uses FIBA as guide	10	100
Misunderstanding among players	5	50

Alleged biases of the referees	4	40
Disagreement on the age bracket for players	3	30
Side comments and complaints from spectators	2	20
Falsification of age	1	10
Protesting/Contesting the results of the game	1	10
Lack of knowledge on the ramifications of games	1	10
Lack of fund for the Liga ng Bayan	1	10
Selection of referees	1	10
Non-attendance of coaches and players during briefing	1	10
Not following the schedule of games	1	10

As indicated in the table, foremost among the difficulties of the Liga Organizers was the absence of manual of operations and guidelines (100%) as well as the misunderstanding among players (50%). As stated by a Liga Organizer, *“Yung hindi pagkaintindihan ng mga players, adda dagijay negative nga ibaga nga madi nasayaat ti referee”*. This is followed by alleged biases of the referees (40%). This is affirmed by a Liga Organizer who remarked, *“uray adda official referee nga binayadan, pagsasawan da pay jay referee ta ti feeling da nasasaor da”*. Another Liga Organizer also expressed, *“Ti ma encounter mi lang madam nga problema nu kua, dagidiay referee nga bias da kanu, isu ti iriri da”*. Disagreement on the age bracket for players (30%) and side comments and complaints from spectators (20%) were also other difficulties involved along with falsification of age, protesting / contesting the results of the game, lack of knowledge on the ramifications of games, lack of fund for the Liga ng Bayan, selection of referees, non-attendance of coaches and players during briefing, and not following the schedule of games.

Section 4. Training Assistance and Needs of Liga Organizers

Table 4 presents the training needs of Liga Organizers.

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Training Needs of Liga Organizers	f	%
Manual of Operations and Guidelines	10	100
Sports clinic	3	30
Training for youth on the rules and regulations of basketball tournament, scheduling of games, making activity designs	1	10
How to implement smoothly activities	1	10
Rules and regulations	1	10
For the SK to conduct the Liga ng Bayan as their program	1	10
Creation of ground rules and assist table management	1	10
Training on sports	1	10

As shown in the table, all (100%) the Liga Organizers expressed the desire to have a manual of operations and guidelines and undergo sports clinic (30%). As one Liga Organizer mentioned, *“Clinic basketball clinic, dagijay kasjay, kasapulan tapnu maadalan pay dagijay ubbing, dagijay baru nga rules, tapos adda kuma pay ti training, seminar para diay nu kasatnu ti panagkarga ti style, tapnu smooth ti implementation”*. Other training needs included training for youth on the rules and regulations of basketball tournament, scheduling of games, making activity designs, implement smoothly sports activities, knowing the rules and regulations, conduct of the Liga ng Bayan by SK as their program, creation of ground rules and assisting in table management by the SK, and training on sports in general.

Providing training to the community organizers is beneficial inasmuch as their morale is improved. Training helps the community organizers to get job security and job satisfaction. The more satisfied the community organizers are, the greater is their morale, the more they will contribute to organizational success. (Kassing et. etl 2004)

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn: The Liga Organizers have good practices in conducting Liga ng Bayan such as holding meetings and making plans in preparation for the game proper, supervising during the game proper, and holding awarding ceremonies and post evaluation after the games. The difficulties encountered by the Liga Organizers consist mainly of misunderstandings among players, alleged biases of the referees, and rules on set qualifications for players. The Liga Organizers expressed their need for assistance especially on the provision of sports clinic.

In the light of the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are forwarded: The Liga Organizers should have a Standardized Manual of Operation and Guidelines where all the important details in the conduct of Liga are found. Liga Organizers should have a common rules and standard in the proper selection of officiating officials. Sports clinic should be conducted and facilitated by recognized basketball experts before and after the liga.

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